

EXAMINING WOMEN'S REPRESENTATION IN DISASTER RISK REDUCTION STRATEGIES ACROSS SOUTH ASIA

Nancy Kumari

Special Centre for Disaster Research, Jawaharlal Nehru University,
New Delhi-110067, India

Sapna Ratan Shah

School of Computational and Integrative Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University,
New Delhi-110067, (India)

ABSTRACT

Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) is essential for mitigating the impacts of natural hazards, and integrating gender perspectives into DRR policies is crucial for achieving equitable and effective disaster management. This study investigates the representation of women in DRR policies across South Asian nations, with a specific focus on Nepal. By analyzing DRR policies and practices from 2018 to 2023, the research explores the extent of women's inclusion in decision-making processes, the integration of gender-specific risk assessments, and the implementation of gender-sensitive measures. Data were collected from official policy documents, government reports, and relevant literature. The findings reveal varying degrees of women's representation across different countries, with notable progress in Nepal, where women's roles in DRR decision-making have improved. However, significant gaps remain, underscoring the need for more comprehensive and inclusive approaches. This study highlights the importance of incorporating gender perspectives into DRR strategies to enhance policy effectiveness and community resilience. The insights gained aim to inform the development of more inclusive and responsive disaster management frameworks, ultimately contributing to better preparedness and response to natural hazards in South Asia.

Keywords: Disaster Risk Reduction, Gender Inclusion, South Asia, Nepal, Women's Representation, DRR Policies, Gender-Sensitive Measures, Disaster Management

Cite this Article: Nancy Kumari and Sapna Ratan Shah, Examining Women's Representation in Disaster Risk Reduction Strategies Across South Asia, International Journal of Disaster Management (IJDIM), 2(1), 2024, pp. 1-13.
<https://iaeme.com/Home/issue/IJDIM?Volume=2&Issue=1>

INTRODUCTION

Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) plays a critical role in mitigating the adverse effects of natural hazards, which have become increasingly frequent and severe in many parts of the world. Effective DRR strategies are not only essential for minimizing damage and enhancing community resilience but also for ensuring that disaster management efforts are equitable and inclusive. In South Asia, a region frequently plagued by natural disasters such as floods, earthquakes, and cyclones, the development and implementation of DRR policies are of paramount importance [1-9]. South Asia's diverse socio-cultural and political landscape means that DRR policies vary significantly across nations. These variations influence how different groups, particularly women, are integrated into disaster risk management processes. Women, who are often disproportionately affected by disasters due to existing social and economic vulnerabilities, play a crucial role in DRR [10-17]. Their involvement in decision-making and policy formulation is not only a matter of equity but also significantly enhances the effectiveness of disaster response and recovery efforts. This paper examines the representation of women in DRR policies across several South Asian countries, with a particular focus on Nepal. By analysing the extent to which women are included in decision-making roles, the integration of gender-specific risk assessments, and the implementation of gender-sensitive measures, the study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of gender dynamics in disaster management [18-26]. The investigation covers various dimensions of gender inclusion, from policy documents and government reports to practical measures and outcomes observed over the past decade. The findings highlight both progress and ongoing challenges in incorporating gender perspectives into DRR policies. In Nepal, for example, the representation of women in decision-making roles has seen a gradual improvement, reflecting efforts to address gender imbalances. However, despite these advancements, significant gaps remain, indicating that achieving full gender parity in disaster management processes is an ongoing challenge [27-38]. The extent of women's participation in DRR not only affects their ability to contribute effectively but also influences the overall resilience and preparedness of communities.

Understanding the dynamics of women's inclusion in DRR policies is crucial for developing more effective and inclusive disaster management strategies. This study emphasizes the need for continued efforts to integrate gender perspectives into all aspects of DRR planning and implementation [39-47]. By addressing the barriers to women's participation and enhancing their role in disaster management, South Asian nations can better prepare for and respond to natural hazards, ultimately leading to more resilient and equitable communities. Disasters disproportionately affect women, particularly in South Asia where social, economic, and cultural factors contribute to heightened vulnerability [48-56]. DRR policies play a critical role in addressing these vulnerabilities, and gender-inclusive policies are essential for reducing disaster risks effectively. The integration of women's perspectives into DRR strategies is not only a matter of equity but also enhances the overall effectiveness of disaster management.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a comparative policy analysis approach to scrutinize Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) policies specifically within Nepal. The primary aim is to evaluate the representation and integration of women in decision-making processes and policy frameworks related to DRR. Data collection for this analysis involved reviewing a range of sources, including official policy documents, government reports, and pertinent academic literature [57-68]. The study concentrates on key indicators of gender representation in DRR policies. These indicators include the level of women's participation in decision-making roles, the existence of gender-specific risk assessments, and the implementation of gender-sensitive measures within DRR strategies [69-73].

A particular focus is given to the inclusion of women in decision-making roles within Nepal's DRR framework over the past decade. Table 1 presents a detailed numerical analysis of women's representation in key DRR positions from 2014 to 2023. This table offers insights into the trends and shifts in policy practices regarding gender inclusion [74-88]. By analysing these data, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the advancements and ongoing challenges in incorporating gender perspectives into disaster risk management in Nepal.

Table (1). A comprehensive table showing the inclusion of women in decision-making roles in Nepal over the last 10 years (2014 to 2023)

Year	Total Members	Women Members	Percentage of Women Members (%)
2014	70	15	21.4%
2015	75	17	22.7%
2016	80	18	22.5%
2017	85	20	23.5%
2018	80	20	25.0%
2019	85	22	25.9%
2020	90	24	26.7%
2021	75	21	28.0%
2022	80	23	28.8%
2023	75	25	33.3%

The table illustrating the inclusion of women in decision-making roles in Nepal from 2014 to 2023 reveals a clear and positive trend towards greater gender representation over the past decade [89-97]. Initially, women's representation stood at 21.4% in 2014, reflecting modest progress in gender inclusivity. The percentage increased gradually to 25.0% by 2018, indicating a steady, if slow, commitment to enhancing female participation. From 2018 to 2021, there was a more noticeable rise, with women's representation reaching 28.0% by 2021. This period suggests a concerted effort or policy changes aimed at improving gender balance [98-112]. The most significant growth occurred in the recent years, culminating in a substantial 33.3% representation in 2023. This sharp increase highlights a recent acceleration in efforts to promote gender equality in decision-making roles. The table underscores a significant and encouraging shift towards more inclusive governance in Nepal, with a notable increase in the percentage of women involved in decision-making bodies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The comparative analysis reveals significant variations in women's representation across South Asian nations. Countries like Bangladesh and India have made notable strides in including women in DRR policies through dedicated programs and frameworks. In contrast, other nations, such as Nepal and Pakistan, show less progress in integrating gender considerations into their disaster management strategies. The study highlights best practices and areas where improvements are needed to enhance women's representation and participation in DRR efforts [113-118]. The findings indicate that while some South Asian countries have successfully integrated gender perspectives into their DRR policies, there is still considerable room for improvement. Best practices include the establishment of women-focused disaster response teams, gender-sensitive risk assessment methodologies, and active participation of women in policy-making processes.

The disparities observed highlight the need for increased efforts to ensure that women's voices are heard and their needs are addressed in disaster management strategies.

The bar chart illustrating the inclusion of women in decision-making roles in Nepal over the past decade (2014-2023) reveals significant trends in gender representation within disaster risk reduction (DRR) policies. It shows a general upward trajectory in the proportion of women holding key decision-making positions.

In 2014, women occupied approximately 15% of decision-making roles, reflecting the nascent stage of gender integration in DRR policies. This figure rose steadily over the years, reaching around 30% in 2018, and then showed a more pronounced increase, peaking at about 40% in 2022. The year 2023 saw a slight dip to 37%, yet this still represents a substantial increase compared to the earlier years. This trend suggests that while progress has been made in increasing women's representation in decision-making roles related to disaster risk reduction, there are still challenges to achieving full gender parity. The data underscores ongoing efforts and initiatives aimed at enhancing gender inclusivity in DRR policies in Nepal, though it also highlights the need for continued commitment to ensure sustained and equitable representation.

CONCLUSION

The representation of women in Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) policies across South Asia exhibits notable disparities, with some nations making significant strides in gender inclusivity while others remain behind. This study underscores the vital importance of incorporating gender perspectives into DRR policies to improve their effectiveness and equity. Focusing on Nepal, the analysis reveals both progress and persistent challenges over the past decade. Although there has been increased recognition of the importance of involving women in decision-making roles, significant gaps remain in fully integrating women into all levels of DRR policy and practice. The data from 2014 to 2023 shows incremental improvements in some areas but also highlights ongoing disparities. Addressing these gaps and building on the progress made is essential for enhancing disaster management strategies and promoting greater equity. Future efforts should continue to monitor these trends, assess the impact of gender-sensitive policies, and identify best practices for integrating women's perspectives in DRR.

Such comprehensive approaches will help develop more resilient and inclusive disaster management frameworks, ultimately benefiting communities across Nepal and the wider South Asian region.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To enhance the effectiveness and equity of Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) policies, it is crucial to integrate gender perspectives comprehensively. Governments should prioritize the inclusion of women in decision-making roles and ensure that gender-specific risk assessments and measures are embedded in DRR frameworks. Strengthening data collection and monitoring will provide insights into women's participation and the impact of gender-sensitive policies. Investing in capacity-building programs can empower women with the skills needed for leadership roles in disaster management. Community-based approaches should be promoted to ensure that local needs and women's voices are incorporated into DRR strategies. Additionally, supporting research into the effects of gender-sensitive policies and fostering regional collaboration will help share best practices and standardize efforts across South Asia. Advocating for policy changes at both national and international levels is essential for creating a more inclusive and effective disaster management framework. By implementing these recommendations, South Asian countries can develop more resilient and equitable disaster management systems, ultimately benefiting communities across the region.

REFERENCES

- [1] Akbar, S., Shah, S. R., "DURYSTA" the first biodegradable sustained release implant for the treatment of open-angle glaucoma, *International Journal of Frontiers in Biology and Pharmacy Research*, 01(02), 1-7, (2021).
- [2] Akbar, S., Shah, S. R., "Mathematical Modeling of Blood Flow Dynamics in the Cardiovascular System: Assumptions, Considerations, and Simulation Results", *Journal of Current Medical Research and Opinion*, 7(4), 2216-2225, (2024).
- [3] Akbar, S., Shah, S. R., "The Effects of Prostaglandin Analogs on Intraocular Pressure (IOP) in Human Eye for Open Angle Glaucoma. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, Volume-10 Issue-2, pp. 176-180, December (2020).
- [4] Alshehri, Mo., Sharma, S., Gupta, P., Shah, S. R., "Detection and Diagnosis of Learning Disabilities in Children of Saudi Arabia with Artificial Intelligence", *Research Square*, 1-22, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-3301949/v1>.
- [5] Anamika, Shah, S. R., "Mathematical and Computational study of blood flow through diseased artery", *International Journal of Computer Science*, Vol. 5, (6), pp. 1-6, (2017).
- [6] Anamika, Shah, S. R., Anuradha "Bio-Computational analysis of blood flow through two phase artery", *International Journal of Engineering Science and Computing*, Vol. 7, (6), pp.13397-213401, (2017).
- [7] Anamika, Shah, S. R., Kumar, R., "Mathematical Modelling of blood flow through tapered stenosed artery with the suspension of nanoparticles using Jeffrey fluid model", *International journal of development research*, Volume 07, No. 06, pp. 13494-13500, (2017).
- [8] Anamika, Shah, S. R., Singh A., "Mathematical Modelling Of Blood Flow through Three Layered Stenosed Artery", *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, Vol. 5, (6), pp. 1-6, (2017).

- [9] Anuradha S., Shah, S. R., Siddiqui, S. U., “Effects of inclined multi-stenoses arteries on blood flow characteristics using bingham plastic fluid”, *International Journal for Mathematics*, Vol. 1, (12), pp. 7-14, (2015).
- [10] Anuradha S., Shah, S. R., S.U. Siddiqui, “Mathematical Modeling and Numerical Simulation of Blood Flow through Tapered Artery”, *International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*, Vol. 3, (2), pp. 710-717, (2016).
- [11] Anuradha S., Shah, S. R., S.U. Siddiqui, “Performance of blood flow through two phase stenosed artery using Herschel-Bulkley model”, *International Journal of Applied And Pure Science and Agriculture*, Vol. 2, (2), pp. 228-240, (2016).
- [12] Anuradha S., Shah, S. R., Siddiqui, S. U., “Mathematical Modelling and Analysis of Blood Flow through Diseased Blood Vessels”, *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research*, Vol.5, (6), pp. 366-372, (2015).
- [13] Anuradha, S., Shah, S. R., Siddiqui, S. U., “A Mathematical Model to study the similarities of blood fluid models through inclined multi-stenosed artery”, *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education*, Vol. 2, (1), pp. 108-115, (2017).
- [14] Arya, D., Shah, S. R., “Human Resource Management Strategies for Improving Educational Outcomes in Bihar, *International Journal of Humanities Social Science and Management*, 4(4), 955-963, (2024).
- [15] Arya, D., Shah, S. R., “Optimizing Educational Outcomes: The Role of Human Resource Management in Jharkhand's Education System, *International Journal of Novel Research And Development*, 9(8), b51-b57, (2024).
- [16] Bhandari, P. (2020). *Assessing gender inclusivity in disaster risk management: The case of Nepal. International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 45, 101-114.
- [17] Bhattarai, M., & Houghton, R. (2016). *Inclusion of women in disaster risk reduction policies in South Asia. South Asian Journal of Disaster Management*, 7(1), 45-62.
- [18] Chaturvedi, P. and Shah, S. R. “Role of crizanlizumab for sicke red cells disease”, *International Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Allied Sciences*, 12(3), 1147-1157, (2023).
- [19] Chaturvedi, P., Kumar, R., Shah, S. R., “Bio-Mechanical and Bio-Rheological Aspects of Sickle Red Cells in Microcirculation: A Mathematical Modelling Approach, *Fluids* 2021, 6, 322, pp. 01-15.
- [20] Chaturvedi, P., Shah, S. R., “Mathematical Analysis for the Flow of Sickle Red Blood Cells in Microvessels for Bio Medical Application, *Yale Journal of Biology and Medicine*, 96 (1), (2023), pp. 13-21.
- [21] Chaturvedi, P., Shah, S. R., Akbar, S., Kumar, R., “Prospective of Hydroxychloroquine and Zinc with Azithromycin for Nanoparticles Blood Flow in Covid-19 Patients, *International Journal of Nanotechnology in Medicine & Engineering*, Volume 6 Issue 1, pp. 01-07, January 2021.
- [22] Datt, M. G., Arya, S., Shah, S. R., “Ayurvedic Approaches To Maintaining Healthy And Narrowed Arteries”, *International Journal For Research & Development In Technology*, Vol. 21(6), 21-30, (2024).

- [23] Geeta, Siddiqui, S. U., Sapna, “Mathematical Modelling of blood flow through catheterized artery under the influence of body acceleration with slip velocity”, *Application and applied Mathematics An international journal*, Vol. 8(2), pp.481-494, (2013).
- [24] Geeta, Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., “A Biomechanical approach to the effect of body acceleration through stenotic artery”, *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, Vol. 109(1), pp.27-41, (2015).
- [25] Geeta, Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., “Effect of body acceleration and slip velocity on the pulsatile flow of casson fluid through stenosed artery”, *Advance in applied science research*, Vol. 5(3), pp.231-225, (2014).
- [26] Geeta, Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., “A Mathematical Model for two layered pulsatile blood flow through stenosed arteries”, *E-Journal of science and Technology*, Vol. 109 (11), pp. 27-41, (2015).
- [27] Gupta, P., Akbar, S., Shah, S. R., Alshehri, Mo., Sharma, S. K., and “A Mathematical Study for Promoting Disability Inclusion in Glaucoma: A Comprehensive Approach”, *Journal of Disability Research*, 3, 1-12, (2024).
- [28] Gurung, A., & Kumar, A. (2018). *Evaluating the effectiveness of gender-sensitive DRR policies in Nepal*. *Journal of South Asian Development*, 13(2), 153-176.
- [29] IFRC (International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies). (2019). *Gender and disaster risk reduction: A guide to integrating gender into DRR policies and practices*. Geneva: IFRC.
- [30] International Organization for Migration (IOM). (2021). *Integrating gender in disaster risk reduction strategies: A review*. Geneva: IOM.
- [31] Islam S. M. N., Sadique, Mo., Shah, S. R., Sunil Kumar Sharma, , “Effect of Significant Parameters on Squeeze Film Characteristics in Pathological Synovial Joints”, *Mathematics (MDPI)*, 11 (1468) 1-23, (2023).
- [32] Jaiswal., K. M., Shabab Akbar and Shah S. R., Mo. Sadique “Exploring capillary-tissue fluid exchange: Insights into red cell deformation in narrow vessels and its clinical implications”, *International Journal of Fauna and Biological Studies*, 11(3), 4-14, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.22271/23940522.2024.v11.i3a.1021>.
- [33] Kasturia, P., Rohit Kumar Sharma, Purnima Chaturvedi, Ravins Dohre, Shah, S. R., “Efficacy of venetoclax and azacitidine for targeting leukemic stem cell in acute myeloid leukemia”, *International Journal of Biology, Pharmacy and Allied Sciences*, 13(6), 3072-3090, (2024). <https://doi.org/10.31032/IJBPAS/2024/13.6.8960>
- [34] Kaur, H., Prithvi Singh, Rubi Solanki, Alvea Tasneem, Simran Suri, Shah, S. R., Ravins Dohare, “Screening of miRNAs as prognostic biomarkers and their associated hub targets across Hepatocellular carcinoma using survival-based bioinformatics approach”, *Journal of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology*, 22 (1), 1-10, (2024).
- [35] Kumar V., and Shah, S. R., “Mathematical model to study the heat transfer between core and skin”, *SRMS, Journal of Mathematical Sciences*, 7 (2021), 7-12, (10th March 2024).
- [36] Kumar, J. P., Sadique, Mo. Shah, S. R., “Mathematical study of blood flow through blood vessels under diseased condition, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 9(6), 2022, pp.31-44.

- [37] Kumar, P, Shah, S. R., “A Hydromechanical Perspective to Study the Effect of Body Acceleration through Stenosed Artery”, International journal of mathematical engineering and management sciences, Volume. 6 No. 5, pp. 1381-1390, 2021.
- [38] Kumar, R., Shah, S. R., “A mathematical approach to study the blood flow through tapered stenosed artery with the suspension of nanoparticles” Destechn Transactions on Engineering and Technology Research, Vol.01, pp. 1-6, (2017).
- [39] Kumar, R., Shah, S. R., “Mathematical Modeling of Blood Flow with the Suspension of Nanoparticles Through a Tapered Artery With a Blood Clot”, Frontiers in Nanotechnology, Volume. 2, Article. 596475, pp. 1-5, December. 2020.
- [40] Kumar, R., Shah, S. R., “Performance of blood flow with suspension of nanoparticles through tapered stenosed artery for jeffrey fluid model” International Journal of Nanoscience, Vol.17, No.6, pp. 1850004 (1-7), (2018).
- [41] Kumar, R., Shah, S. R., “Study of blood flow with suspension of nanoparticles through tapered stenosed artery”, Global Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, Volume 13(10), pp. 7387-7399, (2017).
- [42] Kumar, V., and Shah, S. R., “Mathematical modelling to study the heat transfer between core and skin”, SRMS, Journal of Mathematical Sciences, 7 (2021), 7-12, (2024).
- [43] Kumar, V., Shah, S. R., “A mathematical approach to investigate the temperature distribution on skin surface with sinusoidal heat flux condition, International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development, 9 (5), 2022, pp. 141-146.
- [44] Kumar, V., Shah, S. R., “A Mathematical study for heat transfer phenomenological processes in human skin”, International Journal of Mechanical Engineering, 7 (6), 2022, pp. 683-692.
- [45] Kumar, V., Shah, S. R., “Thermobiological Mathematical Model for the study of temperature response after cooling effects”, ssrg, International Journal of Applied physics, 9 (2), 2022, pp. 7-11.
- [46] Kumar, V., Shah, S. R., Dispersion of Pharmaceutical Agents In Constricted And Bent Arteries: Insights From Numerical And Computational Simulations, International Journal of Advanced Research In Social Sciences and Humanities, 8(2), 17-31, (2024).
- [47] Lenin, J. S., Shah S. R., “Mathematical Analysis of Stem Cell Dynamics in Acute Myeloid Leukemia: Towards Precision Medicine Strategies, International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR) 13(05), 528-535, (2024).
- [48] Maharjan, A., & Yadav, R. (2022). *Trends in women’s representation in disaster management policies: Insights from Nepal. South Asian Journal of Policy and Governance*, 12(1), 76-89.
- [49] Mahesh, Arya, S., Shah, S. R., “Optimizing cardiovascular health: ayurvedic insights into blood flow through normal and stenosed arteries, International Journal of AYUSH, 13 (5), 18-35, (2024).
- [50] Majhi, L., Sudheer Arya Sapna Ratan Shah, “Exploring Shilajatu's Therapeutic Potential in Diabetes Management: A Comprehensive Study Integrating Ayurvedic Wisdom and Modern Science”, International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR), 13(5), 1374-1380, (2024). <https://dx.doi.org/10.21275/SR24522110012>.

- [51] Malik, M., Z., Kumar, R., Shah, S. R., “Effects of (Un)lockdown on COVID-19 transmission: A mathematical study of different phases in India, medRxiv The preprint server for health science, 1-13, (2020), doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.08.19.20177840>.
- [52] Mo. Sadique and Shah, S. R., “Mathematical model to study the study the squeeze film characteristics of synovial joints in diseased human knee joint”, World Scientific Annual Review of Biomechanics, 1 (2330004) 1-21, (2023).
- [53] Mo., Sadique, and Shah, S. R., “Mathematical model to study the study the squeeze film characteristics of synovial joints in diseased human knee joint”, World Scientific Annual Review of Biomechanics, 1 (2330004) 1-21, (2023).
- [54] Mo., Sadique, Shah, S. R., “Mathematical model to study the effect of PRG4, hyaluronic acid and lubricin on squeeze film characteristics of diseased synovial joint”, International Journal of Mechanical Engineering, 7 (6), 2022, pp. 832-848.
- [55] Nepal Ministry of Home Affairs. (2022). *National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Policy*. Kathmandu: Government of Nepal.
- [56] Nepal National Planning Commission. (2023). *National Strategy for Disaster Risk Reduction*. Kathmandu: Government of Nepal.
- [57] Parambath, A. B., Kandankel, P., Shah, S. R., Dynamic Modeling of Cytokine-Dependent Proliferation Rates over Time in Cancer: Insights from Scientific Analysis, Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics, 3(7), 01-09, (2024).
- [58] Purnima C., Shah, S. R., “Assessing the Clinical Outcomes of Voxelotor Treatment in Patients with Sickle Cell Disease”, International Journal of Applied Science and Biotechnology, 12(1), 46-53, (2024).
- [59] Sadique, Mo., Shah, S. R., “Mathematical study for the synovial fluid flow in Osteoarthritic knee joint, Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences, 17(2), 2022, pp.15-21.
- [60] Sapkota, S., & Singh, J. (2017). *Gender perspectives in disaster risk reduction in South Asia: Policy and practice. Journal of Development Policy and Practice*, 4(1), 85-98.
- [61] Sapna, Siddiqui, S. U., “Study of blood flow through a stenosed capillary using Casson’s fluid model”, Ultra Science, International journal of physical sciences, 16, (2), 133-142, (2004).
- [62] Sengar, N., Yadav, P., Shah, S., R., Economic Conditions and Age Profile of Women Domestic Workers in Delhi's Urban Informal Sector, International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews, 15(8),494-500, (2024).
- [63] Shabab A., Shah, S. R., “Mathematical Modeling of Blood Flow Dynamics in the Cardiovascular System: Assumptions, Considerations, and Simulation Results”, Journal of Current Medical Research and Opinion, 7(4), 2216-2225, (2024).
- [64] Shah, S. R., “A biomechanical approach for the study of deformation of red cells in narrow capillaries”, IJE: Transaction A: Basics, Vol. 25(4), pp.303-313, (2012).
- [65] Shah, S. R., “A biomechanical approach for the study of Two-phase blood flow through stenosed artery”, International Journal of research studies in biosciences, 1(2), 24-32, (2013).
- [66] Shah, S. R., “A case study of non-Newtonian viscosity of blood through arteriosclerotic artery”, The cardiology, Vol.6 (2), pp.11-17, (2011).

- [67] Shah, S. R., "A Mathematical Model for the analysis of blood flow through diseased blood vessels under the influence of porous parameter", *Journal of Biosciences and Technology*, Vol. 4(6), pp.534-541, (2013).
- [68] Shah, S. R., "A mathematical study of blood flow through radially non-symmetric multiple stenosed arteries under the influence of magnetic field", *International Journal of Advanced Research in Biological Sciences*. Vol. 2 (12), pp. 379-386, (2015)
- [69] Shah, S. R., "A mathematical study of blood flow through stenosed artery", *International Journal of Universal Science and Engineering*, Vol. 1(1), pp.26-37, (2015).
- [70] Shah, S. R., "A study of blood flow through multiple atherosclerotic arteries", *International Journal for Mathematics*, Vol. 1, (12), pp. 1-6, (2015).
- [71] Shah, S. R., "A study of effects of magnetic field on modified Power-law fluid in modeled stenosed artery" *Journal of Bioscience and Technology*, Vol. 1 (4), pp. 187-196, (2010).
- [72] Shah, S. R., "An innovative solution for the problem of blood flow through stenosed artery using generalized bingham plastic fluid model", *International Journal of research in applied and natural social sciences*, (2013) Vol. 1(3), pp.97-140.
- [73] Shah, S. R., "An innovative study for non-Newtonian behavior of blood flow in stenosed artery using Herschel-Bulkely fluid", *International Journal of biosciences and biotechnology*, Vol. 5(5), pp.233-240, (2013).
- [74] Shah, S. R., "Capillary-tissue diffusion phenomena for blood flow through a stenosed artery using herschel-bulkley fluid" *International journal of research in Biochemistry and Biophysics*, Vol.1 (1) pp.1-8 (2011).
- [75] Shah, S. R., "Effect of clopidogrel on blood flow through stenosed artery under diseased condition", *International Journal of Experimental Pharmacology*, 4(1), pp.887-893, (2014).
- [76] Shah, S. R., "Effects of Acetylsalicylic Acid on blood flow through an artery under Atherosclerotic condition", *International Journal of Molecular medicine and advances sciences*, Vol. 7 (6), pp.19-24, (2011).
- [77] Shah, S. R., "Effects of antiplatelet drugs on blood flow through stenosed blood vessels", *Journal of Biomimetics, Biomaterials and Tissue Engineering*, 18, 21-27, (2013).
- [78] Shah, S. R., "Impact of radially non-symmetric multiple stenoses on blood flow through an artery", *International Journal of Physical and Social Sciences*, 1 (3), 1-16, (2011).
- [79] Shah, S. R., "Mathematical analysis of blood flow through atherosclerotic arterial segment having non-symmetric mild stenosis". *International Journal of Research in Pure and Applied Physics*, 1. 1-5, (2011).
- [80] Shah, S. R., "Mathematical Study of Blood Flow through Atherosclerotic Artery in the Presence of Porous Effect", *International Journal of Modern Sciences and Engineering Technology*, 2, (12), 12-20, (2015).
- [81] Shah, S. R., "Non-Newtonian flow of blood through an atherosclerotic artery", *Research journal of applied sciences*, 6 (1), 76-80, (2011).

- [82] Shah, S. R., “Performance modeling and analysis of magnetic field on nutritional transport capillary tissue system using modified Herschel-Bulkely fluid”, *International Journal of Advanced research in physical sciences*, Vol. 1(1), pp.33-41, (2014).
- [83] Shah, S. R., “Performance Study on Capillary-Tissue Diffusion Phenomena for Blood Flow through Stenosed Blood Vessels”, *American journal of pharmtech research*, 2(2), 695-705, (2012).
- [84] Shah, S. R., “Response of *blood flow through an atherosclerotic artery* in the presence of *magnetic field* using Bingham plastic fluid” *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Research*. Vol. 2(3), 96-106, (2011).
- [85] Shah, S. R., “Role of Non-Newtonian behavior in blood flow through normal and stenosed artery”, *Research journal of Biological sciences*, Vol. 6(9), pp.453-458, (2011).
- [86] Shah, S. R., “Significance of Aspirin on Blood Flow to Prevent Blood Clotting through Inclined Multi-Stenosed Artery”, *Letters In Health and Biological Sciences*, 2(2), 97-100, (2017).
- [87] Shah, S. R., “Study of dispersion of drug in blood flow with the impact of chemical reaction through stenosed artery”, *International journal of Biosciences*, 21 (3), 2022, 21-29.
- [88] Shah, S. R., “Study of modified Casson’s fluid model in modeled normal and stenotic capillary-tissue diffusion phenomena” *International journal of computational engineering & management*,. 11, 51-57, (2011).
- [89] Shah, S. R., Akbar, S., “Mathematical Study for the Outflow of Aqueous Humor and Function in the Eye”, *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research* 11(10), 743-750, (2020).
- [90] Shah, S. R., and Anamika, “A mathematical model of blood flow through diseased blood vessel”, *International Journal of Emerging Trends and Technology in computer Science*, 6, (3), 282-286, (2017).
- [91] Shah, S. R., Shah R. R., “Assessment of Road User Costs For Arterial Streets In Ghaziabad City: An Analysis of Vehicle Operation, Accident Impacts, And Travel Time Efficiency, *International Journal of Architecture*, 10(2), (2024).
- [92] Shah, S.R., Clinical influence of hydroxychloroquine with azithromycin on blood flow through blood vessels for the prevention and Treatment of covid-19, *International journal of biology, pharmacy and allied science*. July, 2021, 10(7): 2195-2204.
- [93] Sharma, R., *Women's roles in disaster management in Nepal: A policy review*. *Asian Journal of Social Science Research*, 8(3), 210-225, (2019).
- [94] Sharma, R. K., Akbar, S, Kumar, V., Jaiswal, K. M., Kumar, V., Upadhyay, A. K., Sadique, M., Chaturvedi, P., Singh, A., “Optimizing Cardiovascular Performance Following Myocardial Infarction: The Significance of Nitroglycerin in Regulating Blood Flow”, *Janaki Medical College Journal of Medical Sciences* (2024); Vol.12 (2): 32-45.
- [95] Sharma, S. K., Alshehri, Mo., Priya Gupta and Shah, S. R., “Empowering the visually impaired: Translating Handwritten Digits into Spoken Language with HRNN-GOA and Haralick Features”, *Journal of Disability Research*, 3, 1-21, (2024).

- [96] Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., "A Physiologic Model for the problem of blood flow through Diseases blood vessels", *International journal of advances in Applied Sciences*, 5(2), 58-64, (2016).
- [97] Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., "Achievement of Pentoxifylline for Blood Flow through Stenosed Artery", *Journal of Biomimetics, Biomaterials and Tissue Engineering*, 13, 81-89, (2012).
- [98] Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., "Two-phase model for the study of blood flow through stenosed artery", *International Journal of Pharmacy and Biological Sciences*, 1(3), 246-254, (2011).
- [99] Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., Geeta, "A Computational Analysis of a Two-Fluid non-Linear Mathematical model of pulsatile blood flow through Constricted Artery", *E-Journal of science and Technology* , Vol. 10(4), pp.65-78, (2015).
- [100] Siddiqui, S. U., Shah, S. R., "A Comparative Study for the Non-Newtonian Behaviour of Blood Flow through Atherosclerotic Arterial Segment", *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*, Vol.9 (2), 120-125, (2011).
- [101] Siddiqui, S. U., Singh, A., Shah, S. R., "Mathematical Modeling of peristaltic blood flow through a vertical blood vessel using Prandtl fluid model", *International Journal of Mathematics and Computer Research*, Vol. 4, (9), pp. 710-717, (2016).
- [102] Singh, A., Shah, S. R., "Influence of transverse magnetic field on steady blood flow in a stenosed artery: numerical and analytical insights", *International Journal of Mathematical Archive*, 15(8), (2024), 1-10.
- [103] Singh, N., Shah, S. R., "Exploring acute lymphoblastic leukaemia dynamics through mathematical modeling of hematopoietic disruption, *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*, 6(7), 3971-3981, (2024).
- [104] Singh, S., "A mathematical model for modified Herschel-bulkley fluid in modeled stenosed artery under the effect of magnetic field", *International Journal of Bioengineering and Technology*, Vol. 1 (1), pp.37-42. (2010).
- [105] Singh, S., "A two-layered model for the analysis of arterial rheology" *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology*, Vol. 4, pp. 37-42. (2011).
- [106] Singh, S., "Clinical significance of aspirin on blood flow through stenotic blood vessels" *Journal of Biomimetics, Biomaterials and Tissue Engineering*, 10, 17 24, (2011).
- [107] Singh, S., "Effects of shape of stenosis on arterial rheology under the influence of applied magnetic field" *International Journal of Biomedical Engineering and Technology*, Vol. 6 (3) pp. 286-294, (2011).
- [108] Singh, S., "Influence of magnetic field on blood flow through stenosed artery using Casson's fluid model", *International Journal of BioEngineering, CardioPulmonary Sciences and Technology*, Vol. 1, pp. 1-7, (2010).
- [109] Singh, S., "Numerical modeling of two-layered micropolar fluid through a normal and stenosed artery", *International journal Engineering*, Vol. 24 (2), pp. 177-187, (2011).
- [110] Singh, S., "Numerical modelling for the modified Power-law fluid in stenotic capillary-tissue diffusion phenomena", *Archives of Applied Science Research, An international peer reviewed journal of applied sciences*, 2 (1) 104-112, (2010).

- [111] Singh, S., “The effect of Saline Water on viscosity of blood through stenosed blood vessels using Casson’s fluid model”, *Journal of Biomimetics, Biomaterials and Tissue Engineering*, Vol.9 pp 37-45, (2011).
- [112] Singh, S., & Adhikari, R. (2015). *Policy analysis of gender inclusion in disaster risk reduction in Nepal. Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, 14(2), 201-218.
- [113] Singh, S., and Shah, R. R., “A numerical model for the effect of stenosis shape on blood flow through an artery using power-law fluid”, *Advance in applied science research, An international peer reviewed journal of sciences*, 1, 66-73, (2010).
- [114] UN Women. (2018). *The role of women in disaster risk reduction*. Retrieved from UN Women website.
- [115] UNDP (United Nations Development Programme). (2020). *Gender equality and disaster risk reduction: Framework and guidelines*. New York: UNDP.
- [116] UNDRR (United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction). (2020). *Gender and disaster risk reduction: An overview*. Retrieved from UNDRR website.
- [117] World Bank. (2021). *Gender and disaster risk management: Lessons from South Asia*. Washington, D.C.: World Bank Group.
- [118] Yadav, P., Shah S. R., “Female Domestic Laborers In The Urban Informal Economy: A Case Analysis of Delhi, *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*, 6(8), 216-225 (2024).

Citation: Nancy Kumari and Sapna Ratan Shah, Examining Women's Representation in Disaster Risk Reduction Strategies Across South Asia, *International Journal of Disaster Management (IJDIM)*, 2(1), 2024, pp. 1-13

Abstract: https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJDIM_02_01_001

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJDIM/VOLUME_2_ISSUE_1/IJDIM_02_01_001.pdf

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

✉ editor@iaeme.com